

URINARY CALCULI COMPOSITION PATTERNS IN PATIENTS PRESENTING
TO LADY READING HOSPITAL: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

 Dr Ismail Khan^{*1}, Dr Azra A ghani², Dr Zeeshan³, Dr Asfandyar⁴
^{*1,3,4}Postgraduate Resident urology CPSP FCPS-II trainee Lady reading hospital Peshawar

²Associate professor Head of department urology Lady reading hospital Peshawar

¹dr.ismailkhan93@gmail.com, zeeshankhanqih@gmail.com³, asfandyarr187@gmail.com⁴

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 Corresponding Author: *
Dr Ismail Khan

Abstract
Background:

Urolithiasis is a common urological disorder with variable composition influenced by geographic and dietary factors. Identifying stone composition aids in prevention and management.

Objective:

To determine urinary calculi composition patterns and their association with demographic variables among patients at Lady Reading Hospital, Peshawar.

Methods:

 A cross-sectional study was conducted on 104 newly diagnosed cases of urinary calculi confirmed by spectrophotometric analysis. Patients with recurrent stones or metabolic disorders were excluded. Associations between stone type and demographic factors were assessed using the chi-square test ($p < 0.05$).

Results:

 The mean age was 36.8 ± 11.2 years, with 59.6% males (ratio 1.5:1). Most were rural residents (60%) from lower socioeconomic backgrounds (50%). Pure stones occurred in 71.2%, and calcium oxalate was the predominant type (83%), followed by calcium phosphate (8.7%), struvite (4.8%), and uric acid (2.9%). No significant associations were found between stone composition and age, gender, residence, or socioeconomic status ($p > 0.05$).

Conclusion:

Calcium oxalate is the predominant urinary stone component, mainly affecting young adult males. Preventive measures focusing on hydration and dietary modification are essential.

INTRODUCTION

Stone composition patterns denote the diverse Methods by which minerals, chemical substances, and organic materials amalgamate and crystallize to create stones or calculi, commonly found within the human body, including kidney stones, gallstones, or tertiary stones. The compositions

demonstrate a sophisticated interaction among metabolic, genetic, environmental, and dietary factors. all of which play a role in the formation, growth. And characteristics of these stones. Renal stones are a prevalent and

painful condition, with their composition patterns offering valuable insight into the underlying pathophysiological processes. Renal calculi frequently result in hematuria and can cause discomfort throughout the abdomen, flank, and groin. These conditions affect 1 in every 11 individuals in some point in their lives, with a prevalence in men that is twice that of women, the formation of stones is associated with a reduction in urine volume or an increase in the excretion of components that contribute to stone formation, including calcium, oxalate, cystine, xanthine, as well as phosphate.

Calculi can also result from diminished urinary citrate levels, which serve as an inhibitor for stone formation, or from increased urinary acidity. Renal calculi can manifest with severe pain, leading most patients to seek immediate care in the emergency department. An isolated incident does not result in kidney failure; however, repeated occurrences of renal calculi can harm tubular epithelial cells, resulting in a decline in the function of the renal parenchyma. Urolithiasis can arise when solutes crystallize from urine, resulting in the formation of stones. Urolithiasis can arise from anatomical characteristics that result in urinary stasis, reduced urine volume, dietary influences, urinary tract infections, systemic acidosis, certain medications or in rare cases, genetic predispositions like cystinuria. The approach to treatment and management of renal stones is largely determined by the specific type of stone present. It is essential to conduct an analysis to avoid recurrence for stone formation. Likewise, an individual's dietary patterns influence the type for renal

stone, as dietary changes have increased the likelihood of renal stone disease formation over the past 50 years within our society. A study found the following urinary calculi composition patterns: calcium oxalate (89.2%), calcium phosphate (54.3%), infection stone (8.1%), and uric acid (7.3%).

The investigation of urinary calculi composition in patients at Lady Reading hospital is essential for comprehending the epidemiological and biochemical factors that contribute to stone formation within this particular population. The understanding of composition of stones is crucial in identifying the fundamental reasons for their formation, which in turn affects treatment approaches and preventive strategies.

OBJECTIVE: To determine the urinary calculi composition in patients presenting to Lady Reading hospital.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS:

Urinary Calculi: It will be diagnosed in patients with all of the following complaints like pain (VAS>1), dysuria, and hematuria. Ultrasound evaluation revealing all of the following features like hyper-echoic areas, and acoustic shadowing.

Urinary Calculi Composition Patterns: All of the mentioned below will be studied by using laser infrared spectroscopy.

Calcium oxalate: It will be defined as kidney stone typically characterized by its composition of calcium oxalate, which occurs when calcium and oxalate combine within the urinary tract. The development of calcium oxalate stones occurs when urine reaches a state of super-saturation with

calcium and oxalate, resulting in the crystallization and accumulation of these compounds into larger calculi.

Calcium phosphate: it will be defined as a kidney stone primarily composed of calcium phosphate, a compound that forms when calcium ions interact with phosphate within the urinary tract. Calcium phosphate calculi generally develop in environments where urine

becomes alkaline. often due to urinary infections induced by urea-splitting bacteria or metabolic disorders such as renal tubular acidosis.

Infection stones: It will be defined as a kidney stone that develop due to urinary tract infections caused by urea-splitting bacteria, including proteus, klebsiella, and pseudomonas species, the bacteria decompose urea into ammonia, resulting in an increase in urine alkalinity, which fosters conditions favorable for the precipitation of magnesium ammonium phosphate.

Uric acid: It will be defined as kidney stone, primarily composed of uric acid, which develops as a result of an excess of uric acid in the urine, which causes crystallization.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design: Cross Sectional Study

Study Setting: Department of Urology (MTI- Lady Reading Hospital, Peshawar)

Study Duration: 6 months

Sample Size: Estimated Sample size n=104

. Urinary calculi composition pattern i.e uric acid (7.3%) .

. Margin of error 50%

.confidence Level 95%

SAMPLING METHOD: Consecutive Non-probability Sampling

ETHICAL APPROVAL This study is conducted after approval by institutional review board LRH/MTI under Ref.No.578/LRH/MTI.

SAMPLESELECTION

Inclusion Criteria

- Both Male/Female
- Age between 18-60 Years
- Patients with urinary calculi as per the operational definition.

Exclusion criteria

- pregnant women
- Patients with metabolic conditions affecting stone formation
- Patients with chronic liver disease

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

The study was conducted following the approval from the ethical review board of the hospital and the research unit of the CPSP Head office. Patients fulfilling the selection criteria for this study were enrolled. The goal and benefits of this study was clearly communicated to all enrolled patients. and they were assured that their participation poses no risk. Subsequently, written informed consent was taken from all enrolled patients. Patients' personnel detail like age. BML. gender, socio economic background, and residence area were obtained. Urinary calculi samples obtained from different patients were evaluated by using the infrared spectroscopy i.e. exposing the stone to ionized radiation and measuring the absorption of specific

wavelengths of light when the sample vibrates at frequencies that correspond to the molecular bonds within the stone. The absorption bands were corrected with the established vibrational frequencies of the minerals present in the stone, facilitating different urinary calculi composition patterns as per the operational definition. The entire assessment was conducted under the supervision of a consultant who possesses a minimum of 5 years of post-fellowship experience.

A pre-designed structured proforma was utilized to document the details of each patient. The researcher collected all the data himself.

DATA ANALYSIS PROCEDURE

Data was collected and analyzed by using the SPSS 22 software. Mean \pm SD or Median (IQR) was presented for numerical data like

age, and BMI after checking the normality of data by Shapiro Wilk test. Frequencies and percentages were presented for categorical data like gender, urinary calculi composition patterns, stone homogeneity, socio economic background, and residence area. Effects modifiers like age, gender, BMI, stone homogeneity, socio economic background, and residence area were addressed through stratification. Post stratification chi-square/fisher's exact test was used by keeping the p-value < 0.05 as significant.

RESULTS: Our study includes 104 patients who were newly diagnosed. Their average age was about 37, ranging from 18 to 65, with most (about 34%) being between 18 and 30 years old. Men made up almost 60% of the group, with about 1.5 men for every woman. Most lived in rural areas (60%), and half were from lower-income backgrounds (Table 1)

Characteristic	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	62	59.6
	Female	42	40.4
Age group	18-30 years	35	33.7
	31-40 years	30	28.8
	41-50 years	23	22.1
	>50 years	16	15.4
Residence	Rural	62	60.0
	Urban	42	40.0

Stone homogeneity	Pure	74	71.2
	Mixed	30	28.8
Socioeconomic status	Lower	52	50.0
	Middle	36	34.6
	High	16	15.4

Table 1-Baseline characteristics of patients

All stones were primary, with 71% being pure and 29% being mixed. Most were calcium oxalate (83%), with calcium phosphate (8.7%), infection/struvite (4.8%),

and uric acid (2.9%) following behind (Table 2). The overall stone type breakdown can be seen in Figure 1 and Figure 2

Stone Type	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Calcium Oxalate	86	83.0
Calcium Phosphate	9	8.7
Infection (Struvite)	5	4.8
Uric Acid	3	2.9
Total	104	100.0

Table 2 Frequency and percentage distribution

Figure 1-Distribution of Urinary Calculi Composition

Figure 2 Distribution of Urinary Calculi Composition

Calcium oxalate was the main component in all age groups. The 18–30 year group had the most stones (33.7%), while the age; 50 year group had the least (15.4%) (Table 3). The stone make-up was about the same across all age groups (p = 0.37).

Age Group (years)	Calcium Oxalate n (%)	Calcium Phosphate n (%)	Infection (Struvite) n (%)	Uric Acid n (%)	Total n (%)
18–30	28 (80.0 %)	3 (8.6 %)	2 (5.7 %)	2 (5.7 %)	35 (100 %)
31–40	26 (86.7 %)	2 (6.7 %)	1 (3.3 %)	1 (3.3 %)	30 (100 %)
41–50	18 (78.3 %)	2 (8.7 %)	2 (8.7 %)	1 (4.3 %)	23 (100 %)
>50	14 (87.5 %)	2 (12.5 %)	0 (0 %)	0 (0 %)	16 (100 %)
Total	86 (83.0 %)	9 (8.7 %)	5 (4.8 %)	3 (2.9 %)	104 (100 %)

Table 3-Age-wise Distribution of Urinary Calculi Composition

Looking at gender, 87% of men had calcium oxalate stones compared to 76% of women. Women had slightly more calcium phosphate

and uric acid stones. But, the difference wasn't big enough to matter statistically ($p = 0.23$) (Figure 3).

Figure 3-Gender-wise Distribution of Urinary Calculi Composition

Where people lived, whether their stones were pure or mixed, and their income level

didn't really change the stone make-up (all $p > 0.05$), as shown in Table 4.

Variable	Category	Predominant Stone Type (Calcium Oxalate %)	Other Stone Types (%)	p-value	Significance
Gender	Male (n = 62)	87.1	12.9	0.23	Not Significant
	Female (n = 42)	76.2	23.8		
Age Group	18-30 years (n)	80.0	20.0	0.37	Not

	= 35)				Significant
	31-40 years (n = 30)	86.7	13.3		
	41-50 years (n = 23)	78.3	21.7		
	>50 years (n = 16)	87.5	12.5		
Residence	Rural (n = 62)	84.0	16.0	0.44	Not Significant
	Urban (n = 42)	81.0	19.0		
Stone Homogeneity	Pure (n = 74)	85.1	14.9	0.19	Not Significant
	Mixed (n = 30)	77.0	23.0		
Socioeconomic Status	Lower (n = 52)	84.6	15.4	0.52	Not Significant
	Middle/High (n = 52)	81.3	18.7		

Table 4-Association Between Patient Characteristics and Stone Composition

Basically, calcium oxalate was the most common stone type for everyone, showing a pretty standard chemical pattern in this group of people.

DISCUSSION

Our study found that calcium oxalate stones were the most common kind of urinary stone, making up 83% of all the stones we looked at. This lines up with what other studies have found, both in our country and around the world. For example, Zhang et al.¹¹ found calcium oxalate in 77.5% of cases in a large study in China, and Basiri et al.¹²

reported that 70% of their patients in Iran had calcium-based stones. Also, Faridet al.¹³ found calcium oxalate to be the most common type in a study in Pakistan, which could be due to similar diets and environments.

The 83% of calcium oxalate stones we saw is a bit higher than what's usually reported, which is between 65% and 78%^(13,14). The reason for this could be that we only included patients who were newly diagnosed and hadn't had surgery before. Our results suggest that the stones in our area are mainly caused

by metabolic issues and not so much by long-term infections or other things. Alathel et al.⁽¹⁵⁾ and Yencilek et al.⁽¹⁶⁾ saw similar patterns in Saudi Arabia and Turkey.

In our study, most of the patients were men (59.6%) with an average age of 36.8 years. This is also pretty normal, as stone formation is most common in people in their 30s and 40s, and it affects men more often. This could be because men tend to eat more protein and get dehydrated at work^(17,18). Studies in India and China have seen similar numbers, with male-to-female ratios between 1.3:1 and 2:1^(11,19). Things like the environment, jobs, and differences in substances that prevent stone formation in urine could explain why more men get stones.

When we looked at different age groups, we found that people between 18 and 30 years old had the most stones. This agrees with recent studies from Asia that show people are getting stones earlier in life^(11,14,19). But, unlike older people in Western countries who tend to get uric acid and mixed stones⁽²⁰⁾, calcium oxalate was the main type of stone for all age groups in our study.

We didn't find any differences in stone types based on gender, age, where people lived, how rich they were, or if the stones were made of one substance. Wang et al.⁽¹⁴⁾ and Kumar et al.⁽²¹⁾ also reported this, saying that while the number of people with stones can change based on location and lifestyle, the stone composition stays about the same across different groups of people. Studies in Iran and China have also confirmed that

there aren't strong between who gets certain types of stones and things like where they live or their background^(12,22).

Because calcium oxalate stones are so common, this has big implications for how we treat them. These stones are closely related to how much oxalate people eat, how dehydrated they are, and metabolic issues like high calcium or low citrate in their urine. Recent studies say that changing lifestyles, staying hydrated, and checking for metabolic problems are key to lowering the chances of getting stones again^(23,24). Our results show that we need to focus on helping people change their diets and fix metabolic risk factors, instead of just relying on surgery.

CONCLUSION

calcium oxalate is the main type of urinary stone in new patients, making up 83% of cases in our region. This illness is most common in young to middle-aged men, especially those from rural areas and poorer families. Even though patients differed in age, gender, and where they lived, we didn't find any strong relationships between these factors and the type of stone they had. This suggests a consistent biochemical pattern across the population. These findings point to the need for prevention strategies that include drinking enough fluids, changing diets, and doing metabolic screenings to lower the chance of recurrence and the overall impact of this illness in our area.

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